

EFFECT OF EMBEDDED FIBER OPTIC SENSOR LENGTH AND ORIENTATION ON SIGNAL PROPERTIES DURING FATIGUE LOADING

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1 Introduction

Currently, composite structures are built with high safety factors to account for constituent material variability and lack of manufacturing repeatability among other factors. They remain in service for a predetermined amount of time and discarded once they pass their predicted lifespan. These practices result in overbuilt/overweight structures that are discarded before they need to be. To overcome this situation embedded fiber optic sensors have been investigated for structural health monitoring.

A type of fiber optic sensor called a fiber Bragg grating (FBG) can be embedded within the composite material during manufacture and used to monitor the fatigue loads induced in the structure. This gives the operator real time knowledge of the condition of the structure during operation allowing them to be built with a lower safety factor and operated until the must be replaced.

Many researchers have investigated the use of embedded or surface mounted FBG sensors for detecting damage composites in real time such as: [1], [2], [3], [4], [5]. A major challenge with embedded FBGs operated under fatigue lies in obtaining a clear and accurate signal. Matrix cracking and the orientation of adjacent reinforcement fibers can cause uneven strain fields in the grating resulting in peak splitting, which causes an offset of the reading obtained from the sensor. With proper FBG selection and reinforcement fiber orientation these problems can be reduced or even eliminated.

2 Background and Theory

To appreciate the results of this investigation a basic understanding of FBGs and fatigue in composites is required.

2.1 Fiber Bragg Gratings

Fiber Bragg Gratings (FBG) are becoming increasingly more popular for many applications due to their advantages such as their size, immunity to electro magnetic interference, multiplexing potential and absolute reading. They have been used to measure properties such as displacement, strain, temperature, pressure, humidity and radiation dose among others.

An FBG is a segment of a single mode optical fiber core with a periodically varying refractive index in the axial (longitudinal) direction [6]. It allows a broad band of light to pass while reflecting a narrow band centered around a wavelength known as the Bragg wavelength, λ_B . The reflected wavelength is a function of the grating pitch (spacing between the refractive index variations), Λ and the average refractive index, n . An FBG satisfies the Bragg condition as:

$$\lambda_B = 2n\Lambda \quad (1)$$

The change in spacing of the periodic refractive index modulation is a function of both strain and temperature. If an FBG sensor is under a mechanical load or temperature variation, the spacing and average refractive index will change, therefore causing a shift in the Bragg wavelength $\lambda_B = (n, \Lambda)$

2.2 Fatigue in Composite Materials

The fatigue behavior of composites is a complex phenomenon due to various types of damage that can occur (fiber fracture, matrix cracking, fiber buckling, fiber-matrix interface failure, delamination, etc.) and interact with each other [7].

Research has shown that the damage process in fiber reinforced composites under fatigue loading is progressive and a combination of various damage modes. The composite goes through three phases. The first phase is characterized by a sharp, non-linear decrease in stiffness attributed to a rapid interconnection of matrix cracking initiated by shrinkage stresses, degree of resin cure, voids and fiber discontinuities. The second phase is characterized by a gradual, linear decrease in stiffness attributed to matrix cracking leading to crack propagation, fiber debonding and delamination. The final stage shows a sharp non-linear decrease eventually resulting in a sudden fiber failure [8].

Figure 1: Reflected FBG spectrum from even strain field (top) and peak splitting resulting from uneven strain field (bottom)

2.3 Fatigue of Embedded FBG

The signal from a typical FBG under an even (consistent) strain field is shown in Figure 1 (top). As observed, a narrow, clean, symmetric peak is reflected back from the FBG. When an FBG is subjected to an uneven strain field various portions of the FBG are under different magnitudes of strain

and therefore reflect a wavelength at the corresponding length. It is almost as though the FBG acts as a number of smaller FBGs. This can result in the reflection of more than one Bragg wavelength as in Figure 1 (bottom). This is known as peak splitting. From multiple reflected peaks it is not possible to determine the average strain by simply tracking the peak wavelength, which is the standard technique used by most FBG interrogation systems.

A typical FBG is 10mm in length. When embedded within a composite it is exposed to a variation of strain magnitude due to the composition of the composite (stiff fibers and a compliant matrix). This results in the aforementioned situation of an uneven strain field, which causes the peak to split and become lost by a typical interrogation system. The use of a shorter FBG, 1mm in length that is aligned with the reinforcement fibers in the composite has the potential to experience a more even strain field and therefore produce an acceptable signal.

3 Experimental Investigation

To investigate the potential benefits of a shorter FBG a number of experiments have been performed. Both 10mm and 1mm long FBGs have been embedded in a glass fiber/epoxy composite and subjected to fatigue loading to failure. During loading the signal from the FBG is monitored. After failure the specimens are sectioned, polished and examined under a microscope.

3.1 Material and Sensors

The laminate selected for this research is $[0/90]_{6S}$ and $[90/0]_{6S}$, glass fiber with epoxy resin. The fiber used is Metyx LT300 E10A 0/90 biaxial E-glass stitched fabric with 161gsm in the 0° orientation and 142gsm in the 90° orientation, summing to 313gsm total. The selected resin is Araldite LY 564 epoxy resin with XB 3403 hardener produced by Huntsman Corporation. The panels undergo an initial cure at 65°C for 24 hours with a post cure at 80°C for 24 hours.

Figure 2 shows a sample of the fabric with a ruler overlaid for reference. The tow width is measured to be roughly 2mm.

3.3 Fatigue Loading

Many challenges lie in the area of fatigue testing of composite materials. They exhibit different characteristics from metallic materials that become apparent during fatigue testing. One such difference between metallic and composite materials is their heat conduction, especially with glass fiber reinforced composites. Autogeneous heating becomes a major concern during fatigue testing of glass fiber reinforced composites as the built up heat is not conducted to the environment as it is with metallic materials. The fatigue properties of composite materials are especially sensitive to heat. ASTM standard D3479 states that a temperature increase of 10°C has demonstrated measurable property degradation [9]. Generally a fatigue loading frequency of 1-4Hz for glass fiber has been used with no heating [10]. This results in a lower testing frequency, which in turn results in extended time to perform an adequate test study.

All fatigue tests are constant amplitude strain, tension-tension sine wave tests. The maximum and minimum load and displacement is recorded. The minimum stress on the specimens is 27.6MPa while the maximum load is determined as a fraction of the maximum stress of 318.75MPa; 0.4 or 0.5 depending on the test. The magnitude of the minimum load was selected based on that used by Natarjan [8] in a similar study. To determine the displacement amplitude to obtain the desired strain, a simple calibration procedure is performed: the specimen is loaded into the machine and a load that will produce the desired amount of stress is slowly applied and released, then applied and released a second time. When the specimen is unloaded there is a residual displacement sensed by the LVDT. This is due to the wedge grips tightening and the specimen slipping slightly before the full clamping force is realized. This zero offset only occurs during the first loading cycle, after that the displacement returns to zero when the load is returned to zero. To account for this nonlinear phenomenon the zero-offset is subtracted from the maximum displacement on the second loading cycle. The fatigue tests are then run at this displacement.

For this study a number of specimens with embedded FBGs have been produced using the resin transfer molding technique (RTM). They have been

cut into tensile test coupons according to ASTM D3039. A gripping fixture has been designed to interface with the specimen and an MTS 322 test frame with MTS 647 hydraulic grips to allow for the fiber optic to egress from the composite without a load applied to it.

The tests were conducted with a sinusoidal load at 4Hz with a constant amplitude strain of 0.4 and 0.5 times the ultimate strain of the material. The peak of the FBG was interrogated with a Micron Optics SM230 interrogator at a rate of 100Hz. Due to the fatigue frequency (4Hz) the reflected spectrum could not be recorded.

3.4 Microscopy Preparation and Inspection

To prepare specimens for microscopic inspection, sections were cut from the full size specimen after it was fatigue tested, polished and examined. These specimens were prepared with three slightly different techniques.

To prepare the first specimens, two lines were drawn down the middle of each specimen perpendicular to the loading direction. The specimens were cut along these lines with a water jet cutter. Three samples were acquired from each specimen. The cut surface, which is perpendicular to the optical fiber was then polished. First 400 grit abrasion was applied to the surface by hand, then 1000, 1500, 2000 grit polishing was performed with a polishing machine. All polishing was performed in water to prevent an adverse increase in temperature and maintain dust.

In order to investigate the cracks located along the fiber direction, both samples had to be cut along the loading direction. Due to practical reasons and the limited size of the specimens, a water jet system could not be used; a hand held rotary tool was used instead. After locating the optical fibers inside the samples, a line was drawn along the fiber direction. A cut was made along this line. The sample with the optical fiber now close to the surface was then polished. First, 320 grit and 400 grit abrasion is applied by hand. However, investigation of the surface under optical microscope revealed high surface roughness. Therefore, another polishing process was applied with 1000, 1500, 2000 and 3000 grit abrasion. This process was done by hand under water. New samples were gathered and the same

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procedure was applied. All these samples were then investigated under an optical microscope in bright field, reflected light mode.

After the initial inspection, it was decided that new samples be cut from the specimens. In this case, the surface along the fiber direction was to be analyzed. After locating the fiber inside the specimen, a line was drawn down the center. This time a circular diamond saw was used. The machine has a water injection system to prevent heat build-up. The samples that contain the optical fiber close to the surface were polished. This time a polishing machine was used for the whole process. Since the surface was smooth after the cut, abrasion started from 1500. After, 2000 and 3000 grit abrasion was put on the rotation wheel and sample surfaces were polished. These surfaces were then analyzed under optical microscope in bright field, reflected light mode again.

4 Results and Discussion

All tests were run until the specimen failed. Depending on the magnitude of loading the specimens ran for up to six days. FBG data was recorded during testing and the specimens were inspected under a microscope after failure to determine the crack density.

4.1 Data Acquisition

The effects of the different FBG lengths and orientations are quite evident in the collected data. Essentially, with a 1mm long FBG that is oriented in-line with adjacent reinforcement fibers there is no lost data (data recorded as 0 due to a lost signal).

Figure 5 shows the data collected from a specimen with a 10mm long FBG embedded perpendicular to adjacent reinforcement fibers. Initially there is no loss of signal as can be seen in the first eight seconds (upper plot). This continues for the initial 5% of the cycles before data points are regularly lost. All data points are recorded during the lower loading (troughs) but are lost (and recorded as 0) during higher loading (peaks). This can be clearly seen in the bottom plot of Figure 5.

Figure 5: 10mm long FBG: Initial eight seconds (top), final eight seconds (bottom)

Figure 6: 1mm long FBG: Initial eight seconds (top), final eight seconds (bottom)

Figure 6 shows the data collected from a specimen with a 1mm long FBG embedded in line with the reinforcement fiber. It can be seen that the data points are recorded at virtually every time step from the initial cycles (Figure 6 top) up to failure (Figure 6 bottom).

4.2 Inspection

After failure, the specimens were sectioned, polished and examined under a microscope. The density of matrix cracking was measured in order to correlate the effect of the crack spacing and FBG length.

Figure 7: Microscopic image of cross sectioned specimen after fatigue test

Figure 7 shows a cross section of the specimen after fatigue testing. A number of cracks can clearly be observed in the figure. The average crack density was measured to be roughly 1.1mm. It can also be seen that the tow width when RTM'd into the composite corresponds to that measured in Figure 2 (2mm).

Figure 8: Microscopic image of cross section of embedded optical fiber

The interaction between the fiber optic and the composite was also inspected in order to determine

if the FBG was debonding inside the laminate, which may be contributing to the lost signal. Figure 8 shows a cross section of the embedded fiber optic. It appears that there is no debonding or negative interaction with the composite. The large scratch that is visible in Figure 8 is a result of abrasive polishing.

4.3 Discussion

The challenge with embedding FBG sensors in composites lies in ensuring that they are under an even strain field. Three factors influence the consistency of the field thereby enabling FBGs to reliably monitor strain during fatigue loading.

The first factor is the relationship between FBG length and tow width. In a composite made with NCF material, tows (bundles of fiber) are stitched together to make up a fabric. Once the composite is processed, the regions between the tows are resin rich compared to those regions within the tows. The stiffness of the resin rich areas is less than within the tow since there is only resin and no glass fiber to increase the stiffness. This results in an uneven strain field across a number of tows when a load is applied.

In the material used in the study the tow width is on the order of 2mm. This is greater than the length of the 1mm long FBGs and less than the 10mm FBGs. At most a 1mm long FBG will experience one resin rich area while a 10mm long FBG will experience four resin rich areas. The more excessive variation in strain seen in a longer FBG results in a broader reflection spectrum and in some cases causes a loss of the ability to track the peak wavelength. Figure 9 describes this configuration and shows the relative sizes of FBGs and tow width.

In line with the concept of maintaining an even strain field by reducing the number of tows that cross an FBG the reinforcement fiber orientation also plays an important role. If the fiber optic is embedded in-line with the reinforcements that it is in contact it will experience a less uneven strain field. Figure 9 shows the two possible optical fiber/fiber reinforcement orientations. The experimental results show that optical fibers oriented in-line with the reinforcement (Figure 9 right) had a sharper reflected spectrum and were therefore more reliable.

Figure 9: Schematic of embedded FBG

The crack density plays a similar role to tow width in maintaining a consistent strain field. When a crack in the composite develops the region within that area experiences a greater strain than the intact composite since there is nothing holding the crack together. The area adjacent to the crack experiences much less strain since the load is relieved by the crack.

The crack density in our specimens that were examined under a microscope is around 1.1mm. This is slightly larger than the 1mm long FBGs. On average the 1mm long FBGs will experience one crack (higher strain region) while the 10 mm long FBG could experience nine cracks. This reinforces the fact that the 1mm long FBGs produced better data than the 10mm long FBGs.

5 Conclusion

The challenge with embedding FBG sensors in composites to accurately monitor strain lies in ensuring that they are under an even strain field. When an FBG is under an uneven strain field the reflected spectrum will broaden and eventually split into a number of peaks. This results in either a loss of signal or an inaccurate signal due to a peak shift caused by the split.

To embed FBGs in an even strain field three factors should be kept in mind: i) tow width to FBG length relationship, ii) optical fiber and adjacent reinforcement fiber orientation, and iii) crack density resulting from fatigue loading.

The tow width should be greater than the length of the FBG so it only experiences one region of uneven strain (the resin rich area between the tows).

The optical fiber should be aligned with the direction of the adjacent reinforcement fibers that it

is embedded next to. This further reduces the uneven strain field found between tows.

Ideally the crack density should be equal to or greater than the FBG length. Cracked regions have more strain in the local vicinity compared to the intact region and therefore contribute to an uneven strain field in a similar manner to the resin rich regions between tows.

Experimental results show that the signal from a 1mm long FBG embedded in-line with adjacent reinforcement fiber within a NCF material with tow widths of ~2mm, and a 1.1mm crack density after fatigue testing is much more reliable than a 10mm long FBG embedded perpendicular to adjacent tows.

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References

- [1] Y. Okabe, S. Yashiro, T. Kosaka, N. Takeda, "Detection of transverse cracks in CFRP composites using embedded fiber Bragg grating sensors", *Smart Materials and Structures*, 2000.
- [2] Y. Okabe, T. Mizutani, S. Yashiro, N. Takeda, "Detection of microscopic damages in composite laminates", *Composites Science and Technology*, 2002.
- [3] C.S. Shin, C.C. Chiang, "Fatigue damage monitoring in polymeric composites using multiple Bragg gratings", *International Journal of Fatigue*, 2006.
- [4] D.C. Betz, G. Thursby, B. Culshaw, W.J. Staszewski, "Acousto-ultrasonic sensing using fiber Bragg gratings", *Smart Materials and Structures*, 2003.
- [5] H. Tsuda, "Ultrasound and damage detection in CFRP using fiber Bragg grating sensors", *Composites Science and Technology*, 2006.
- [6] A. Othonos, K. Kalli, G.E. Kohnke, "Fiber Bragg Gratings: Fundamentals and Applications in Telecommunications and Sensing", *Artech House Inc.*, Boston, 1999.
- [7] B. Harris, "Fatigue in Composites", *Woodhead Publishing Limited*, Cambridge, 2003.
- [8] V. Natarajan, H. Gangarao "Fatigue response of fabric-reinforced polymeric composites". *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2005.

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- [9] ASTM International, "ASTM D3437 Standard test method for tension-tension fatigue of polymer matrix composite materials," Feb. 2010.
- [10] W. Van Paepegem, I. De Baere, E. Lamkanfi, and J. Degrieck, "Monitoring quasi-static and cyclic fatigue damage in fibre-reinforced plastics by Poisson's ratio evolution," *International journal of fatigue*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 184–196, 2010.